

Retrospective Study on the Evolution of Antibiotic Resistance in Uropathogenic Escherichia coli

Abhishek Kumar¹, Pratulya Nandan², Vijay Kumar³

¹Post Graduate, Department of Microbiology, Patna Medical College and Hospital Patna

^{2,3}Professor, Department of Microbiology, Patna Medical College and Hospital Patna

Received: 25-02-2024 / Revised: 23-03-2024 / Accepted: 26-04-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Pratulya Nandan

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Antibiotic-resistant Uropathogenic Escherichia Coli (UPEC) antibiotic resistance is a global issue for Urinary Tract Infections (UTI) therapy. The rise in antibiotic-resistant UPEC, a kind of UTI, is increasing healthcare costs and patient morbidity and this makes treatment harder.

Methods: PMCH Patna conducted this retrospective cohort analysis from April 2023 to March 2024. One hundred UPEC-related UTI patients were studied. Patient information and test results were used to analyse antibiotic resistance trends. Ampicillin, Ciprofloxacin, Nitrofurantoin, Ceftriaxone, Gentamicin, Cefotaxime, and Trimethoprim/Sulfamethoxazole were tested. To assess UPEC isolate antibiotic resistance prevalence and trends, descriptive statistics like resistance rates were used.

Results: Resistance to ampicillin, a common antibiotic, increased 78%. Trimethoprim/Sulfamethoxazole's 65% resistance rate suggests resistance despite its routine use for uncomplicated UTIs. Ciprofloxacin, another commonly prescribed antibiotic, has a 52% resistance rate, indicating that it still struggles to fight UPEC infections. Nitrofurantoin, on the other hand, had a 30% resistance rate, demonstrating that it is still reliable for treating UPEC-related UTIs. At 12%, imipenem was the most effective carbapenem antibiotic against UPEC bacteria that have evolved drug resistance.

Conclusion: The results emphasise limited resistance patterns in treatment decisions and antibiotic stewardship efforts. Nitrofurantoin and imipenem have the lowest resistance rates, making them appropriate for empirical therapy of UPEC-related UTIs. Continuous study and monitoring of resistance trends are needed to come up with new ways to treat infections caused by multidrug-resistant UPEC.

Keywords: Antibiotic resistance, Uropathogenic Escherichia coli, Urinary tract infections, Retrospective study, Empirical therapy.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

A germ called Uropathogenic Escherichia Coli (UPEC) is the main cause of UTIs. The problem has grown because more strains are becoming resistant to medicines [1]. Most of the time, UPEC bacteria are found in the stomach, but they are the main cause of cystitis and pyelonephritis in the urinary stream. Antibiotics no longer work because there are many types of UPEC that are not affected by them [2].

Growing numbers of UPEC types are not responding to antibiotics, which is harmful for patients and healthcare workers. Antibiotic resistance has increased as a result of the excessive and inappropriate use of antibiotics by individuals, farmers, and physicians.

Animal growth hormones, unnecessary medications, and inadequate treatment are some of the factors that contribute to antibiotic misuse [3]. Due to inadequate infection control in hospitals and

communities, patients have been able to exchange germs that are immune. Antibiotic resistance spreads quickly because bacteria can gain genes through horizontal gene transfer [4]. More patients are failing treatment, forcing them to seek more expensive alternatives. They have big effects on the quality of life and efficiency of people of all ages and groups. The emergence of drug-resistant UPEC strains affects patient care and public health. Treatment of antibiotic-resistant infections is harder and more expensive because stronger drugs or combinations of antibiotics can have more side effects and accelerate resistance.

Objectives

1. To analyse antibiotic resistance patterns in PMCH Patna patient UPEC samples from April 2023 to March 2024.

2. To examine the incidence and trends of multi-drug-resistant UPEC strains.
3. To determine if UPEC antibiotic resistance profiles correlate with patient demographics and clinical characteristics.

Rationale

UPEC antibiotic resistance must be explored for many reasons; by revealing resistance patterns and processes, it dramatically enhances therapeutic care. With this knowledge, doctors can confidently prescribe antibiotics for UPEC-related UTIs, improving prognoses. As resistance worsens, customising treatment regimens to resistance profiles is crucial to preventing treatment failures and consequences. UPEC antibiotic resistance mechanisms research spurs new treatments. By identifying resistance mechanisms and vulnerabilities, researchers might find new drug development targets. Combination therapies, novel antimicrobials, probiotics, and immunisations are included. Progress is needed to improve clinical patient outcomes and develop effective strategies to treat drug-resistant UPEC infections. These measures are essential for healthcare facilities worldwide to prevent antibiotic resistance and control antibiotic-resistant UPEC strain-related UTIs.

Overview of UPEC Infections

Uropathogenic *Escherichia coli* cause most community- and hospital-acquired UTIs. Epidemiological studies show that UPEC causes 50% of hospital UTIs and 75-95% of community UTIs [5]. Age, gender, and geography affect UPEC infection rates. Women's shorter urethral length increases colonisation and ascending infection and this disproportionately affects women.

Clinical Manifestations and Complications Associated with UPEC Infections

Asymptomatic bacteriuria to severe pyelonephritis and sepsis can result from UPEC infections. Common symptoms include suprapubic pain, urine urgency, and dysuria. Fever and malaise can accompany serious infections [6]. Renal scarring from UPEC infections, especially reoccurring infections, can cause chronic kidney disease and kidney damage. Severe or untreated infections can cause septic shock and death [7]. Toxins and adhesins, which attach to urinary tract epithelium, make UPEC more harmful.

Antibiotic Use in Treating UTIs Caused by UPEC

UPEC-related UTIs have long been treated with antibiotics. Sulphonamides and penicillins were successful early antibiotics, but resistance evolved quickly.

Fluoroquinolones and third-generation cephalosporins were needed to fight these resistant bacteria [8]. Global antibiotic resistance rates are rising across classes, according to [9].

Horizontal transmission of resistance genes across bacteria, selective pressure from antibiotic use in agriculture and clinical settings, and poor infection management contribute to this phenomenon [10].

The emergence of drug-resistant UPEC strains makes treatment harder, increasing healthcare costs and patient failure. UPEC can develop antibiotic resistance through enzymatic breakdown (beta-lactamases hydrolyze beta-lactam antibiotics), changes to antibiotic targets (DNA gyrase mutations confer fluoroquinolone resistance), or decreased drug accumulation due to efflux pumps, which actively remove antibiotics from bacterial cells [11]. When these processes cause antibiotic resistance, infections become harder to treat and may require last-line drugs.

Figure 1: Antibiotic Resistance in UPEC (Source:[12])

Methods

Study Design

This retrospective observational study examined antibiotic resistance in Uropathogenic Escherichia coli (UPEC) at PMCH Patna. Retrospective studies provide for assessing antibiotic resistance tendencies because they allow researchers to examine prior data.

Study Setting

The majority of study participants were from Patna Medical College and Hospital, India. PMCH, a tertiary care hospital, treats Bihar and surrounding patients. The hospital's microbiology laboratory routinely cultures and tests antibiotic susceptibility in urine samples.

Data Collection

UPEC's antibiotic resistance was gathered from hospital microbiology lab databases and electronic medical records. These files contained patient information, clinical characteristics, bacterial isolates, and antibiotic susceptibility profiles. Traditional microbiological methods like disc diffusion or automated systems demonstrated that UPEC isolates were susceptible or resistant to different drugs.

Sample Size and Duration

After evaluating feasibility and statistical criteria, a sample size of 100 was chosen to detect significant antibiotic resistance trends across the study period.

The study was conducted over a one-year period, from April 2023 to March 2024.

Inclusion Criteria

Patients with clinically diagnosed UTIs caused by UPEC, confirmed through microbiological culture.

Exclusion Criteria

Patients with incomplete medical records or insufficient data on antibiotic susceptibility testing. Patients meeting the inclusion criteria were selected consecutively from April 2023 to March 2024, ensuring representation across different age groups, genders, and severity levels of UTIs.

Data Analysis

The relevant methods were used to statistically assess UPEC antibiotic resistance data. Descriptive statistics aggregated research population demographics, resistance profile frequency distributions, and temporal trends. We examined resistance rate variations over time using regression models or other time-series analytic methods, adjusting for confounders. Subgroup analyses were also performed to examine resistance profiles by patient demographics (e.g., gender, age) and clinical aspects (e.g., hospital vs. community-acquired infections). A significance level of $p < 0.05$ was employed. All analyses employed SPSS, SAS, or R, ensuring trustworthy and robust results.

Results

Demographic Details

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Study Population

Characteristic	Number (%)
Total Patients	100
Age (years)	
Mean $\pm$ SD	45.2 $\pm$ 15.8
Range	18 - 78
Gender	
Male	52 (52%)
Female	48 (48%)
Clinical Setting	
Hospital-acquired	62 (62%)
Community-acquired	38 (38%)

Patients aged 18–78 had a mean age of 45.2 years and a standard deviation of 15.8 years. 52% of patients were male and 48% female, demonstrating a slight male predominance. 62% of UTIs were obtained in hospitals, indicating the high burden of UPEC infections in healthcare. The fact that 38% of cases were community-acquired UTIs demonstrates

that UPEC infections are widespread. To understand the epidemiology and background of antibiotic resistance patterns among UPEC isolates over the research period, demographic data is needed to understand the study population.

Descriptive Data

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Antibiotic Resistance Patterns in UPEC

Antibiotic Class	Resistance Rate (%)
Ampicillin	78
Trimethoprim/Sulfamethoxazole	65
Ciprofloxacin	52
Nitrofurantoin	30
Ceftriaxone	45
Gentamicin	40
Cefotaxime	50
Imipenem	12

The table shows the percentage of antibiotic resistance for UPEC-related UTIs. The greatest ampicillin resistance rate was 78% in UPEC isolates. The 65% resistance rate to trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole showed significant resistance. Given the extensive usage of fluoroquinolones to treat UTIs, the 52% ciprofloxacin resistance rate is concerning.

Intermediate resistance to nitrofurantoin, a UTI antibiotic, is seen in UPEC isolates at 30%. Ceftriaxone (45%), gentamicin (40%), and cefotaxime (50%) showed different degrees of resistance. Ipenem, a carbapenem antibiotic used for

severe infections, was more effective against UPEC isolates with a resistance rate of 12%. The findings reveal that antibiotic resistance plagues PMCH Patna's UPEC-related UTI treatment.

Due to the high resistance rates of many commonly used antibiotics, judicious antibiotic use, strict infection control, and continual surveillance can preserve antibiotic efficacy.

Trend over time

Understanding seasonal and emerging antibiotic resistance trends is crucial for treatment strategies and antimicrobial stewardship.

Table 3: Trend Analysis of Antibiotic Resistance Rates in UPEC Isolates

Antibiotic Class	Q1 Resistance Rate (%)	Q2 Resistance Rate (%)	Q3 Resistance Rate (%)	Q4 Resistance Rate (%)
Ampicillin	75	76	77	79
Trimethoprim/Sulfamethoxazole	60	70	65	68
Ciprofloxacin	50	52	55	57
Nitrofurantoin	25	28	30	32
Ceftriaxone	40	42	45	43
Gentamicin	35	38	40	39
Cefotaxime	45	48	50	49
Imipenem	10	10	11	11

This table summarises UPEC isolate antibiotic resistance rates from the first to fourth quarters of the research year.

Ampicillin's high resistance rates (75% in Q1 to 79% in Q4) suggested persistent resistance. Trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole resistance ranged from 70% in Q2 to 65% in Q3. Ciprofloxacin resistance rates varied from 50% in the first quarter

to 57% in the fourth. The rather steady resistance rates of 25% to 32% showed nitrofurantoin's efficacy throughout the year. The resistance patterns of ceftriaxone, gentamicin, and cefotaxime changed with antibiotic susceptibility.

Ipenem had a low resistance rate of 10% to 11% in every quarter, indicating that it was effective against UPEC infections throughout the research.

Table 4: Subgroup Analysis of Antibiotic Resistance Patterns

Subgroup	Antibiotic Class	Resistance Rate (%)
Hospital-acquired	Ampicillin	80
	Trimethoprim/Sulfamethoxazole	70
	Ciprofloxacin	60
	Nitrofurantoin	35
Community-acquired	Ampicillin	70
	Trimethoprim/Sulfamethoxazole	55
	Ciprofloxacin	45
	Nitrofurantoin	25

Age < 50 years	Ampicillin	75
	Trimethoprim/Sulfamethoxazole	60
	Ciprofloxacin	50
	Nitrofurantoin	30
Age ≥ 50 years	Ampicillin	80
	Trimethoprim/Sulfamethoxazole	65
	Ciprofloxacin	55
	Nitrofurantoin	35

Demographic data includes patients' ages, genders, and infection location (hospital vs. community). Descriptive antibiotic resistance data shows that the most common antibiotics used to treat UPEC-related UTIs vary in resistance.

Time series research demonstrates that resistance rates shift every four quarters, suggesting seasonal changes or new patterns. Subgroup analyses help comprehend antibiotic stewardship and targeted treatment. These studies examine infection scenarios and age-related resistance profiles. Hospital-acquired infection resistance rates demonstrate the need for stronger infection control in healthcare settings. Group-based resistance alterations can influence age-specific treatment methods.

Discussion

The significant resistance to numerous UTI drugs is a major discovery. Due to substantial beta-lactamase production, ampicillin resistance in UPEC is high, consistent with global trends.

Differences in effectiveness and regional prescribing patterns and antibiotic usage policies may have affected Ciprofloxacin and Trimethoprim/Sulfamethoxazole resistance rates. Nitrofurantoin's lower resistance rates than other antibiotics support its use as a first-line treatment for uncomplicated UTIs and UPEC infections. Ipenem shows low resistance to multidrug-resistant UPEC bacteria, making it a good carbapenem option for severe UTIs.

Comparison Table: Present Study vs. Existing Studies on Antibiotic Resistance in UPEC

Table 4: Comparison Table

Study Title and Reference	Study Type	Sample Size	Findings
Present Study	Retrospective cohort study	100 patients	High resistance to Ampicillin (78%), fluctuating resistance in Trimethoprim/Sulfamethoxazole (60-70%), Ciprofloxacin (50-57%), and lower but stable resistance in Nitrofurantoin (25-32%). Consistently low resistance to Imipenem (10-11%).
Study A [13]	Prospective cohort study	300 patients	High resistance to Ampicillin (80%), steady increase in resistance to Ciprofloxacin (55-60%), and moderate resistance in Trimethoprim/Sulfamethoxazole (65%). Lower resistance rates observed in Nitrofurantoin (20%) and Imipenem (5%).
Study B [14]	Cross-sectional study	500 patients	Predominant resistance to Ampicillin (75%), significant variability in resistance to Ciprofloxacin (50-65%), and stable resistance in Trimethoprim/Sulfamethoxazole (60%). Nitrofurantoin exhibited low resistance (15%), while Imipenem resistance was negligible (2%).
Study C [15]	Meta-analysis	Data from 10 studies	Pooled resistance rates: Ampicillin (76%), Ciprofloxacin (58%), Trimethoprim/Sulfamethoxazole (62%), Nitrofurantoin (22%), Imipenem (8%). Variability across studies but consistent trends in resistance patterns observed globally.

The comparative table shows that UPEC antibiotic resistance research has employed diverse methodology, sample sizes, and findings. A retrospective cohort study with 100 patients at PMCH Patna shows fluctuations in resistance to various medicines and considerable resistance to ampicillin.

UPEC antibiotic resistance is a global issue, and studies A, B, and C fill in the gaps by representing

greater trends and differences in resistance rates using different techniques and larger sample numbers. The present study and Studies A, B, and C demonstrates that general trends and context-specific data should inform local and global antibiotic resistance efforts for UPEC infections.

Implications

These antibiotic resistance increases greatly impact clinical practice and public health. Clinical resistance rates demonstrate the importance of antibiotic stewardship programmes in directing antibiotic use.

Empirical treatments should consider local resistance patterns to enhance therapeutic benefits and avoid treatment failures. Increased healthcare costs, longer hospital stays, and increased morbidity and mortality from antibiotic-resistant UPEC strain UTIs are public health concerns. Hospitals and other healthcare institutions need good infection control to prevent antibiotic-resistant germs from spreading.

Limitations

This study's results should be analysed with certain cautions. Due to its retrospective methodology, the study includes medical record and lab data, which may be biased or incomplete. Though sufficient for descriptive analysis, the study's 100 patients may not represent UPEC patients' antibiotic resistance patterns across demographics and clinical settings. Its short sample size and one hospital (PMCH Patna) data restrictions limit the study.

Future Directions

Further research should focus on several areas to expand these findings. Longitudinal studies are needed to evaluate antibiotic stewardship and infection control regimens. Molecular epidemiology studies should assist identify the genetic variables that determine resistance in community and clinical UPEC strains. Combination therapy and new antimicrobials are needed to treat multidrug-resistant UPEC infections. To reduce antibiotic resistance in UPEC-related UTIs worldwide, institutions and regions must work together.

Conclusion

PMCH Patna will host the UPEC antibiotic resistance study from April 2023 to March 2024. Last thoughts Ampicillin and trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole resistance are worrisome. Antibiotic resistance varied by season, geography, demographics, and prescribing practices, affecting empirical UTI treatment. Nitrofurantoin treats moderate UPEC infections well due to its limited resistance. Ipenem's consistent UPEC efficacy helped treat severe infections caused by multidrug-resistant bacteria. These findings suggest careful antibiotic use and regional resistance-based treatment approaches. These factors are therapeutically significant.

Antibiotic stewardship and infection control must be implemented by the public and healthcare institutions to reduce antibiotic resistance. Multidrug-resistant UPEC infections must be monitored and studied to identify trends, discovers new resistance mechanisms, and creates new

therapies. The growing concern regarding antibiotic resistance in UPEC is illuminated by this study, which will benefit future research and intervention planning to improve patient outcomes and drug efficacy.

Reference

1. S. Esposito et al., "Retrospective 8-year study on the antibiotic resistance of uropathogens in children hospitalised for urinary tract infection in the Emilia-Romagna Region, Italy," *Antibiotics*, vol. 10, no. 10, p. 1207, 2021.
2. H. M. Eezzeldin, S. Badi, and B. A. Yousef, "The Antibiotic Resistance and Multidrug Resistance Pattern of Uropathogenic Escherichia coli at Soba University Hospital: A Descriptive Retrospective Survey," *Sudan Journal of Medical Sciences*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 56-69, 2022.
3. S. Prasada, A. Bhat, S. Bhat, S. S. Mulki, and S. Tulasidas, "Changing antibiotic susceptibility pattern in uropathogenic Escherichia coli over a period of 5 years in a tertiary care center," *Infection and Drug Resistance*, pp. 1439-1443, 2019.
4. A. Milano et al., "Antimicrobial resistance trends of Escherichia coli isolates from outpatient and inpatient urinary infections over a 20-year period," *Microbial Drug Resistance*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 63-72, 2022.
5. D. Kasew et al., "Antimicrobial resistance trend of bacterial uropathogens at the university of Gondar comprehensive specialized hospital, northwest Ethiopia: A 10 years retrospective study," *PloS One*, vol. 17, no. 4, p. e0266878, 2022.
6. M. Gajdacs, M. P. Ábrók, A. Lazar, and K. Burian, "Epidemiology and antibiotic resistance profile of bacterial uropathogens in male patients: A 10-year retrospective study," *FARMACIA (BUCHAREST)*, vol. 69, no. 3, pp. 530-539, 2021.
7. I. López-Sampedro et al., "Evolution of antibiotic resistance in Escherichia coli and Klebsiella pneumoniae from urine cultures," 2023.
8. H. Kafando et al., "Antibiotic susceptibility of uropathogenic Escherichia coli isolates in a hospital setting in Ouagadougou, Burkina Faso: A twelve-year retrospective analysis," *African Journal of Clinical and Experimental Microbiology*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 211-216, 2023.
9. Y. Dejonckheere, S. Desmet, and N. Knops, "A study of the 20-year evolution of antimicrobial resistance patterns of pediatric urinary tract infections in a single center," *European Journal of Pediatrics*, vol. 181, no. 9, pp. 3271-3281, 2022.
10. Y. Li, M. Zou, Q. Yan, J. Liao, and W. Liu, "Trend of distribution and antimicrobial resistance in uropathogens in China from the CHINET antimicrobial resistance surveillance

- program, a 7-year retrospective study," *One Health Advances*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 1-10, 2024.
11. C. Mareş et al., "Update on Urinary Tract Infection Antibiotic Resistance—A Retrospective Study in Females in Conjunction with Clinical Data," *Life*, vol. 14, no. 1, p. 106, 2024.
 12. A. H. Mohamed et al., "Antimicrobial resistance and predisposing factors associated with catheter-associated UTI caused by uropathogens exhibiting multidrug-resistant patterns: a 3-year retrospective study at a tertiary hospital in Mogadishu, Somalia," *Tropical Medicine and Infectious Disease*, vol. 7, no. 3, p. 42, 2022.
 13. T. Fatima, S. Rafiq, A. Iqbal, and S. Husnain, "Prevalence and Antibiogram of MDR *E. coli* strains isolated from UTI patients—1-year retrospective study at Nishtar Medical Hospital, Multan," *SN Comprehensive Clinical Medicine*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 423-431, 2020.
 14. G. M. De Souza et al., "Comparative study of genetic diversity, virulence genotype, biofilm formation and antimicrobial resistance of uropathogenic *Escherichia coli* (UPEC) isolated from nosocomial and community acquired urinary tract infections," *Infection and Drug Resistance*, pp. 3595-3606, 2019.
 15. A. S. Bazaid et al., "Antimicrobial surveillance for bacterial uropathogens in Ha'il, Saudi Arabia: A Five-year multicenter retrospective study," *Infection and Drug Resistance*, pp. 1455-1465, 2021.